

Adoption of Computer Based Procedures and the Associated Challenges

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ABSTRACT

Computer Based Procedures have been proposed for implementation in Nuclear Power Plants since the early 1980s. Although new construction facilities have partially implemented this approach, there are no existing plants within the United States that have fully adopted Computer Based or Electronic Procedures. There is sufficient research to indicate that Computer Based Procedures provide a useful tool to operators. However, there is little research on the return on investment. An analysis of previous industry events can demonstrate situations in which the use of CBPs could mitigate a future event.

INTRODUCTION

The accident at Three Mile Island Nuclear Generating Station in 1979 demonstrated a need for improvements to control room operator human performance (Eisenhut, 1980). The United States Nuclear Regulatory Commission (NRC) and leading vendors within the nuclear industry investigated the event, publishing NUREG-0737 *Clarification of TMI Action Plan Requirements* was published which outlined actions for the industry based on the initial investigation.

The Institute for Nuclear Power Operations (INPO) was established in 1979. INPO implemented standards of industry-wide performance objectives, criteria, and guidelines for nuclear power plant operations. Principles for procedure development, verification and validation were also established. Many of these standards were instrumental in building the basis for the next forty years of focus on Operator Fundamentals and improvements to Human Performance.

Early research indicated that 65% to 69% of plant events were related to human factor issues involving a procedure deficiency (Stanton, 1996, p106 and Goodman & DiPalo, 1991). Industry-wide focus was established on procedure improvements and the associated human factors tools. In more recent studies, academic and industrial research for nuclear procedures has focused on the transition of Paper Based Procedures (PBPs) to Computer Based Procedures (CBPs) (Oxstrand & Blanc, 2016 and Oxstrand & Bly, 2017).

CBPs are those procedures which provide a computer interface to access the procedure. In some cases, the CBP may provide interface with system parameters or include automation. Electronic Procedures (EPs) are considered electronic static displays of the PBP, yet often providing the ability for place keeping, step tracking and real time updates of procedure completion.

The NRC and the Electric Power Research Institute (EPRI) have published regulation and industrial guidance for CBPs and EPs. Many other international regulatory and supporting bodies have followed this trend. There is a consensus that CBPs have a benefit to operations and human factors, but the extent of that improvement is currently unknown. CBPs have not been adopted by existing operators of nuclear power plants within the United States. Research is needed to examine how CBP adoption could potentially mitigate loss of generation and thus demonstrate a clear a return on investment.

PROCEDURE TYPES AND USAGE

Operating procedures specify a series of steps that need to be taken to complete a specific action. Although PBPs are most commonly used in nuclear power plants, extensive research has been performed on the implementation of CPBs and EPs for various types of procedures. These procedure types are aligned to EPRI terminology (Naser, 2007):

- *Normal Operating Procedures (NOPs)*
For normal operation, an NOP is utilized to perform an initial line-up, fill, vent, start up, shut down and also provides guidance on routine operation.
- *Alarm Response Procedures (ARPs)*
Due to the large number of parameters that are constantly monitored, irregular parameters will cause an alarm in the control room or other local operating stations. The majority of alarms will require action from the operator or further investigation. In the event of exceeding pre-determined setpoints for a parameter, ARPs provide the operator actions to execute. These setpoints include high and low level indications in tanks, high or low flow conditions, high or low temperature conditions, disconnection of communications with remote equipment and many other irregular parameters.

- *Surveillance Test Procedures (STPs) and Periodic Test Procedures (PTPs)*
STPs and PTPs are used to test the equipment which is necessary to operate the Nuclear Power Plant (NPP) and include operation of emergency equipment or other equipment important to nuclear safety. Many of these tests are performed to meet regulatory requirements as part of the operating license.
- *General Operating Procedures (GOPs)*
GOPs provide steps for the interrelated plant lineups during fill and vent, startup, shutdown and refueling. These procedures include administrative protocols and refer to other STPs, PTPs and NOPs. These procedures act as standard procedures for operation of the plant, a sequencing document for the activity and a formal document for retention of permissions and readiness.
- *Abnormal Operating Procedures (AOPs)*
During abnormal operation, an AOP is utilized to perform the actions necessary to restore the system to normal and operation. The AOP may be utilized due to loss of flow, loss of water level, excessive vibration, cavitation of pumps, restoration from automatic safety actions and other abnormal conditions.
- *Emergency Operating Procedures (EOPs)*
EOPs are utilized to address a reactor trip and establish a safe shutdown condition. These procedures also assess and address design basis accidents. Typical accidents that are addressed in EOPs are Loss of Coolant Accident, Steam Generator Tube Rupture and an Excess Steam Demand.

Detailed implementing procedures are utilized for the maintenance of plant equipment and components, treatment of wastewater, addressing radiological conditions and other activities associated with the operation of the power plant. These procedures are typically PBPs, but frequently considered for use in CPBs and other types of EPs in research applications (Le Blanc & Oxstrand, 2012). Administrative procedures are used in the nuclear industry with every administrative and support function. These procedures are typically PBPs only.

HYBRID CONTROL ROOMS

The main control room (MCR) is the primary control center from which operators view the status of the plant and take actions necessary to startup, shutdown, and maintain safe operation. The majority of MCRs in the United States were constructed using analog control systems. As NPPs upgrade outdated systems, digital control systems are routinely introduced in a phased approach. System upgrades occur during refueling outages, which typically last only 25 to 45 days each 18 to 24 months, with insufficient time to make comprehensive multi-system changes.

As a result, most MCRs in the United States are a complex hybrid of analog and digital control systems. Hybrid MCRs can provide operators with over 2,000 indications and several hundred controls, which aid in monitoring and operating the power plant (Lew et al., 2018).

Construction of fully digital nuclear power plants is ongoing in the United States and in many places throughout the world. In the United States, Southern Company is in the final phases of construction of two AP1000 reactors in Georgia. China, India, South Korea and the United Arab Emirates are currently building additional nuclear capacity. These digital MCRs have tens of thousands of system parameters, which are constantly monitored by automatic control systems.

Barakah Nuclear Power Plant (BNPP) comprises four units of the Advanced Power Reactor (APR-1400) reactor with a total capacity of 5.6 GWe (Esmail & Cheong, 2021). The MCR of the APR-1400 power plant includes several types of Man-Machine Interface systems which includes a Computerized Procedure System (CPS) (Government of the UAE, 2017). The APR-1400 Final Safety Evaluation states the CPS is compliant with NUREG-0711 requirements (Korea Electric Power Corporation, 2019). The APR-1400 CPS provides instructions directly on one of four displays for each of the MCR operators. The system supports access to information from plant instruments. Operators may view the progress and performance of steps through the CPS (Choi et al., 2018).

From January 2017 to June 2019, extensive testing was performed as part of a detailed Human Reliability Analysis (HRA) on the APR-1400. The Korea Atomic Energy Research Institute in cooperation with EPRI and Korea Hydro and Nuclear Power (KHNP) performed these tests. Analysis focused on AOPs and EOPs (Y. Kim, 2020).

Five primary areas of concern of the CPS were identified (Choi et al., 2018):

- Team performance may be impacted due to the lack of communication required between the operators (H. Kim et al., 2020).
- Situational awareness may be reduced due to a reliance on computerized procedures (Murungi & Jung, 2016).
- A limitation of parallel processing may result in the keyhole effect (Y. Kim et al., 2019).
- Operators are primarily trained on CPS and should be ready to transition to PBPs upon a failure of the CPS (Kramer, 2000).
- Automation of plant manipulation should be carefully evaluated. For example, hold steps during EOPs may be able to auto-progress to the next step when the conditions specified are met (Kaber & Endsley, 2004).

On the other hand, similar observations determined that the use of CBPs could bring significant improvements (Lew et al., 2018).

- Fewer operator errors due to improvements in human factors.
- Fewer procedure deviations due to a reduced complexity of communications.
- Recovery from human error is faster compared to recovery with PBPs.
- Logic may be utilized within the body of the CBP to provide indication of step satisfaction with input from multiple instruments at the same time.
- CBPs can monitor continuous action steps and alert the operator when the specific condition has been met.
- The use of CBPs reduces memory dependent demands on operators and reduces the need to track multiple conditions simultaneously.

ADOPTION IMPLICATIONS

Adoption of CBPs will result in a significant investment of utility capital. This implementation will also result in higher operating costs. Associated cost may include (Thomas et al., 2016):

- Increased administrative cost from the standpoint of engineering design change and all applicable licensing documents.
- Development of the interactive CBPs require additional knowledge, skills and abilities which a typical procedure writer may not possess.
- Operators must be able to transition from CBPs to PBPs in the event of a CPS failure. Effective procedures must be maintained in both PBP format and CBP format with identical content. In most cases, this does not facilitate a paper-less environment.

For another consideration, existing procedures at most US NPPs are the product of continual improvement over the life span of the facility, with input from hundreds of operators. These procedures contain extensive operating experience and input that may be lost if converted to CBPs without thoughtful consideration of each step.

Although implementation of CBPs have not been embraced at existing NPPs, KEPCO and Westinghouse have implemented CBPs on new construction units (Ha et al., 2007 and Wen, 2010). However, there is no existing data on the exact cost associated with the implementation of a CBP system at an existing power plant.

Research and assertions have stated that CBPs will provide a reduction in control room and field operator workload, which result in significant savings (Thomas et al., 2016). However, these assertions include a full implementation of CBPs and

EPs for all Operating Procedures. For the case of implementing CBPs for EOPs and AOPs only, this reduction of workload and associated cost-benefit is not present. Additionally, based on current requirements for transitioning to PBPs upon a loss of the CBP System, there is no benefit associated with a reduction of PBPs in the MCR for EOPs and AOPs alone. A full implementation of CBPs and EPs would be required for all Operating Procedures to actualize this cost benefit.

Utility operators are aware of the human performance benefits when implementing a CBP System for EOPs and AOPs. Nevertheless, these human performance benefits have not been linked to a specific cost. It is clear that a reactor trip due to a human performance error leads to a loss of generation. Industry data indicates that an uncomplicated reactor trip without material deficiencies can cost up to 3 days of loss of generation over \$1 million USD per day (Lew et al., 2018). However, there is little evidence to support a return on investment based on loss of generation alone.

EVENT ANALYSIS

A total of 50 reactor trip events were reviewed which involved procedure issues. Reviews were performed on information provided from Licensee Event Reports (LER) available on the NRC's public website. Each event was evaluated for contributors associated with human performance, procedure use and adherence, control room burden and adequacy of procedural guidance. Events were also evaluated to determine if CBPs or EPs could have potentially mitigated the event. The following 12 events were identified which involve human performance associated with procedure execution.

Events which could have been mitigated by a Computer Based Procedure System:

- On 12 November 2021, Beaver Valley Unit 2 was in Mode 1 at approximately 17 percent power following a refueling outage. A manual reactor trip was initiated due to increasing steam generator water levels due to oscillating Main Feedwater Pump Recirculation Valves. The oscillation of the valves led to a steam generator water level transient that met predefined reactor trip criteria. The direct cause was the key lock switches for the recirculation valves were left in AUTO allowing the valves to modulate based on flow indication. The unit supervisor did not properly read a procedure step from a startup procedure and the step was not performed. Corrective action to address human performance issues was to enforce standards of self check and peer check. This event resulted in a loss of generation. This event may have been avoided if the GOP and associated NOP was a CBP. (Nuclear Regulatory Commission, 2021a)

- On 12 October 2020, DC Cook Unit 2 was in Mode 1 at approximately 100 percent power. An automatic reactor trip occurred due to exceeding the low-low steam generator automatic reactor trip setpoint. This direct cause was the Startup Flash Tank was not fully isolated and the tank outlet valves remained open, causing condenser vacuum to lower, eventually causing steam driven main feed pumps to trip. This event occurred due to local operators missing a step in the NOP. Corrective actions to address human performance issues included several procedure enhancements and enforcement of pre-job briefs. This event resulted in a loss of generation. This event may have been avoided if the NOP had been a CBP. (Nuclear Regulatory Commission, 2020)
- On 12 May 2019, McGuire Unit 1 was in Mode 1 at approximately 100 percent power following a maintenance outage. While executing the GOP associated with steady-state operation, an operator error occurred with control of the pressurizer pressure master controller. This caused reactor coolant system pressure to decrease below the Over Temperature Delta Temperature (OTDT) setpoint, which resulted in an automatic reactor trip. The operator took action contrary to the existing Paper Based Procedure. However, effective use of existing AOPs and ARPs would have mitigated this event in PBP format. Corrective actions to address human performance issues included training solutions and reinforcement of operator fundamentals and standards for procedure use and adherence. This event resulted in a loss of generation. Computerized Procedures would have provided a reduced burden for control room operators and ease of access to these additional procedures, which may have mitigated the event. (Nuclear Regulatory Commission, 2019)
- On 20 August 2010, South Texas Project Unit 1 was at 100 percent power. During performance of a routine surveillance test on the solid state protection system, the reactor operator inadvertently skipped two pages of the test procedure. One of the many steps that were skipped included blocking a turbine trip signal, which was subsequently inserted. This resulted in an automatic turbine trip and reactor trip. Corrective action to address human performance issues was to enforce standards of procedure use and adherence. This event resulted in a loss of generation. This event would have been avoided if the STP had been a CBP. (Nuclear Regulatory Commission, 2010)
- On 14 August 2003, Ginna Nuclear Power Plant was at 100 percent power. A major electrical grid disturbance occurred, affecting the Northeastern United States and Southern Canada. A reactor trip occurred due to the load rejection and the operating crew executed the EOP as expected, which resulted

in the plant stabilizing in Mode 3 with natural circulation. When main feedwater pumps were stopped, motor driven auxiliary feedpumps started automatically. During recovery operations, one of the motor driven auxiliary feedpumps were damaged due to pump alignment issues. This was caused due to a missed procedure step. This event resulted in a loss of generation due to extending the recovery operations. This event would have been avoided if the NOP had been a CBP. (Nuclear Regulatory Commission, 2003)

Events which would have not been mitigated by a Computer Based Procedure System:

- On 21 November 2021, Calvert Cliffs Unit 2 was in Mode 1 at 100 percent power. While attempting to start a spent fuel pool cooling pump for post maintenance testing, an arc-flash event occurred. The loss of the associated load center and resulting transient caused a loss of all steam generator feed pumps. The reactor was manually tripped by the operating crew. The cause of the event was the installation of insulating breaker cubicle stab covers without a formal tracking method, which were not removed after maintenance. This event would not have been mitigated by the use of a CBP for maintenance procedures. Existing Paper Based Procedures did not include the use of stab covers or properly track the use of stab covers. (Nuclear Regulatory Commission, 2021b)
- On 19 October 2018, Oconee Unit 1 was in Mode 1 at approximately 19 percent power performing a downpower for a refueling outage. The Abnormal Operating Procedure for degraded condenser vacuum was entered due to a failed auxiliary steam supply valve, which resulted in lowering vacuum. An automatic reactor trip was imminent; however, operators took inappropriate action to start the motor driven emergency feedwater pumps, which caused an introduction of colder feedwater and an associated reactivity management event. This event would not have been mitigated by the use of a CBP, as operators intentionally deviated from the existing PBP. (Nuclear Regulatory Commission, 2018)
- On 03 July 2017, Oyster Creek Unit 1 was in Mode 1 at 100% percent power. The augmented offgas system tripped following a grid disturbance. The AOG system normal operating procedure and the associated Alarm Response Procedure did not contain sufficient guidance to isolate the system on a trip. Failure to realign the AOG system to a shutdown lineup resulted in the AOG Flame Arrestor syphoning into the lower section of the Offgas delay pipe. The steam jet air ejector became ineffective due to the water in the delay pipe from AOG. This resulted in

degrading main condenser vacuum. Control room operators inserted a manual scram prior to the low Main Condenser vacuum automatic scram setpoint being reached. This event would not have been mitigated by the use of a CBP. Existing PBPs were inadequate to address the condition. (Nuclear Regulatory Commission, 2017)

- On 20 May 2017, Beaver Valley Unit 2 was in Mode 1 at 17 percent reactor power with power ascension in progress after a refueling outage. Steam dumps were acting as a load for the reactor and heat removal was being maintained with one condensate pump and one feedwater pump. As the operating crew was raising power, a feedwater system recirculation valve lineup led to abnormally low feedwater pump suction pressure. The GOP and the feedwater system NOP were not adequately integrated for ease of use during power escalation. When the operating crew started a second condensate pump, operators were unable to control steam generator water level, eventually leading to a required manual trip of the Reactor. This event would not have been mitigated by the use of a CBP system. Existing PBPs were inadequate to address the condition. (Nuclear Regulatory Commission, 2014)
- On 06 October 2011, Seabrook Unit 1 was in Mode 1 at 100 percent reactor power. While restoring a condensate pump from maintenance, air was introduced into the condensate system, which resulted in momentary cavitation of the two operating condensate pumps. One of the operating feedwater pumps tripped on loss of suction pressure, which resulted in a turbine runback. An automatic reactor trip occurred due to low steam generator water level. The cause of the event was lack of guidance in the instructions for clearance restoration and inadequate procedural guidance in the NOP. There was no procedure to fill, vent and restore a condensate pump at power. This event would not have been mitigated by the use of a CBP. (Nuclear Regulatory Commission, 2011)

CONCLUSION

Based on previous research, it is clear that adoption of CBPs provides numerous benefits. Current advancements in CBPs have focused on EOPs and AOPs. However, there is no clear return on investment for implementation of only EOPs and AOPs. In order to realize the true cost-benefit of employing a CBP system, NPP operators should fully implement CBPs for all Operations Procedures.

Additionally, the LER analysis demonstrates that transition from PBPs to CBPs will not automatically result in improved human performance. CBPs will not remove requirements for sufficient training, qualifications and basic operator fundamentals. Industry focus should remain on development of PBPs with sound engineering principles, operating experience and proper human factors. An accurate and easy to use procedure is a fundamental requirement for operation of the NPP, regardless of the method of presentation.

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